

PREPARATION OF CARBONACEOUS PARTICLES FOR PRODUCTION OF CAST Zn-Al MATRIX COMPOSITES BY RHEOCASTING METHOD.

Luis Javier Cruz Riaño¹.

¹*News Materials Group, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana, A. A. 56006, Medellín, Colombia.*

SUMMARY: In this paper a systematic study was undertaken to investigate the effect of pre-heat-treat on reinforcing particles for the preparation of Zn-Al alloy – carbonaceous particles composite by rheocasting method. The heat pretreatment required for the dispersion of the uncoated carbonaceous particles in zinc alloy melts consists of heating the carbonaceous particles to 500° C in air for 1 h just prior to their dispersion in the melts. The expulsion of volatile matter and surface mordentation from particles when they are heat-treated was in fact confirmed by SEM analysis. It was possible to disperse up to 5% vol. carbonaceous particles in ZA 27 alloy semisolid and retain the particles in a well distributed fashion in the casting using the pre-heat-treated carbonaceous particles. The ZA 27 – 5% vol. carbonaceous particles composite made using pre-heat-treated particles has a tensile strength of 405 MPa with 9,5% elongation.

KEYWORDS: Rheocasting, Zn-Al alloy, carbonaceous particles, particles composites, surface modification, processing.

INTRODUCTION.

Discontinuous composites form an important category of materials used in engineering applications. Of the several methods available for combining a metal matrix with a reinforcement (fibres or particles) to manufacture metal matrix composite (MMCs), casting processes stand out as remarkably simple and economical [1,2,3]. They are thus gaining in importance, both commercially and in the scientific literature. Rheocasting could be a suitable technique for low cost mass production of MMCs [4]. Nevertheless, more investigation has to be performed in order to evaluate and to improve the mechanical performances of this type of MMC. The major difficulty of this process is poor wettability [5] of most of the ceramic particles due to the molten alloy which makes the incorporation and retention of the particles in the liquid extremely difficult.

Attempts have been made to solve this problem through several approaches: (a) adding metal coated particle in molten alloy [6] using the vortex or gas injection technique, (b) the addition of uncoated particles with the aid of ultrasonics and simultaneous additions of surface and interfacial active elements [7].

In this paper a systematic study was undertaken to investigate the effect of pre-heat-treat on reinforcing particles for the preparation of Zn-Al alloy – carbonaceous particles composite by

rheocasting method. The contact angle of Zn-Al alloy with SiC is 157° and it is reported to remain unwettable between the melting point of alloy and 600 °C [8].

MATERIAL PREPARATION.

Material used.

Zinc-aluminium alloy of the following nominal composition was used as the base alloy to make the composites: Zn-26.6Al-2.3Cu-0.016Mg and carbonaceous particles with size up to 63 μm were used as reinforcement.

Preparation of carbonaceous particles.

Initially, the carbonaceous particles were subjected to drying, milling and sieving in order to obtain an adequate particle size. The particles were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA). The results (Figura 1) show that between 250 °C and 450 °C, little oxidation occurs on particle surface. Intensive degradation does not begin until a temperature of approximately 480 °C is reached. The information provide by the TGA curve in Figure 1 is valuable in that it shows the need to preheat the reinforcement to 480 °C.

Fig. 1: Thermal analysis of the reinforcer

Then, about 30 g. of carbonaceous particles were subjected to isothermal heating at 500 °C and 600 °C in air atmosphere (Figure 2). The Figure 2 indicate that it would be possible to remove most of the volatile substances and adsorbed gases present in the carbonaceous particles by heating the carbonaceous particles to 500° C for about 60 min when the height of particles is about 20 mm. However, severe oxidation and great degradation of carbonaceous particles was observed at 600° C of activation temperature. Therefore, 500° C was selected as the optimum temperature for expelling the volatile substances and adsorbed gases and for introducing a moderate superficial mordentation on the particles. The expulsion of volatile matter and surface mordentation from particles when they are heat-treated was in fact confirmed by SEM photographs, Figure 3.

Fig. 2: Isothermal heating of carbonaceous particles in air at different temperatures.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3: SEM photographs of heat-treated carbonaceous particles: (a) Unheat-treated, (b) at 500 °C for 90 min and (c) at 600 °C for 90 min.

Preparation of composites.

The experimental set-up, Figure 4, consist of a pit type electrical resistance melting and holding furnace and a stirrer assembly. About 2 kg of the alloy was placed in crucible and heated to above its liquidus temperature. The mixer were lowered in the melt and rotation begun at 447 r.p.m. The themperature in the liquid-solid range was 470 °C. The controller was adjusted to hold the slurry at this temperature while mixing continued. The treated carbonaceous particles were then added into the slurry through a mechanical injection system at a rate of 5 g. per min. At the conclusion of charging, the melt was allowed to mix isothermally for another 15 min, and cast into suitable permanent molds.

Fig. 4: Photographs of the experimental set-up.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION.

Microstructural characterization of the cast Zn alloy carbonaceous composites was done by both optical and SEM studies. The tensile test was done using a 10 ton Instron machine. The fracture surfaces (tensile) of the composite specimens were observed under SEM to understand the type and nature of fracture of these cast composite.

Initial attempts to disperse untreated carbonaceous particles in zinc alloy melts led to total rejection of the particles from the melt. However, the treated particles were mechanical entrappment and homogeneously distribution in the alloy matrix for 3 vol.%, and even 5 vol.%. The microstructure and good distribution of particles in ZA27 with 5 vol.% carbonaceous composite are shown in Figure 5. The distribution of carbonaceuos particles appears to be reasonably uniform in the alloy matrix, and distinct individual particles can be seen.

The ZA 27 – 5% vol. carbonaceous particles composite made using pre-heat-treated particles has a tensile strength of 405 MPa and its failure strain of 9,5% at working length of 50 mm. Examinations of the tensile fractured surfaces show that there are no visible voids around the particles and that the matrix appears to have failed by ductile fracture. In areas where carbonaceous particles are present, brittle type of fracture is seen (Figure 6).

Fig. 5: Distribution of particles in ZA27-C_p 5 vol pct composite. Unetched, 200X.

Fig. 6: SEM photographs of fracture surface of cast ZA27-C_p 5 vol. pct composite.

CONCLUSIONS.

1. It was not possible in the present investigation to disperse carbonaceous particles in ZA27 alloy semisolid when unheat-treated carbonaceous particles were used.
2. Apparently, preheating the carbon to 500 °C for 90 minutes removes the adsorbed gases and volatile substances, and induced an surface mordentation, thereby improving the wettability between the carbonaceous particles and the ZA 27 semisolid.
3. It is possible to disperse up to 5 vol.% of uncoated but pre-heat-treated carbonaceous particles in ZA27 alloy semisolid by the rheocasting method. The mechanical properties of ZA27-5 vol.% carbonaceous particle composites made in the present investigation are better than ZA27 alloy in its initial condition.

REFERENCES

1. Rohatgi, P. K., Asthana, R. and Das, S., "Solidification, structure, and properties of cast metal-ceramic particle composites", *International Metals Review*, Vol. 31, N^o. 3, 1986, pp. 115-139.
2. Rohatgi, P. K., "Cast metal-matrix composites", *Metals Handbook*, Vol. 15: Casting, Ninth Edition, ASM International, Metals Park, Ohio, pp. 840-854.
3. Allison, J. E. and Cole, G. S., "Metal-matrix composites in the automotive industry: opportunities and challenges", *JOM*, January 1993, pp. 19-24.
4. Giroto, F. A., Albingre, L., Quenisset, J. M. and Naslain, R., "Rheocasting Al matrix composites", *Journal of metals*, November 1987, pp. 18-21.
5. Mehrabian, R., Riek, R. G., and Flemings, M. C., "Preparation and casting of metal-particulate non-metal composites", *Metallurgical Transactions*, Volume 5, August 1974, pp. 1899-1905.

6. Seah, K. H. W., Sharma, S. C., and Girish, B. M., "Mechanical properties of cast ZA-27/graphite particulate composites", *Materials & Design*, Vol. 16, N° 5, 1995, pp. 271-275.
7. Murali, T. P., Surappa, M. K., and Rohatgi, P. K., "Preparation and properties of Al-alloy coconut shell char particulate composites", *Metallurgical Transactions B*, Volume 13B, September 1982, pp. 485-494.
8. Fletcher, T. R., Russell, K. C., and Cornie, J. A., "Wetting of SiC particles by Zn-Al alloys", Final Report of ILZRO, 1988, pp. 1-39.